

NOTES

Complexes of Tetravalent Uranium

Part I. Triphenyl Phosphite Complexes of U(IV)*

SABYASACHI SARKAR

Post-graduate Department of Chemistry, T. D. College, Jaunpur (U.P.)

Received 2 February 1971.

The studies of Horrocks and Taylor¹ showed that the phosphite is a poorer σ -donor than the phosphine but a better π -acceptor. However, phosphine complexed compounds of many transitional metals are known² and in the case of phosphite, trialkylesters substituted complexes of a few transition metals, specially those of Pt-metals are known³. In this communication, the preparation and chemical properties of two forms of triphenylphosphite complex of U(IV) are presented.

Aqueous methanolic (1 : 1) solution (20 ml) of uranylacetate (2 gm) is mixed with 30 ml concentrated HCl and the hexavalent uranium is reduced with metallic zinc till the colour of the solution changed from yellow to bright green. Excess of the stoichiometric amount (4 ml) of freshly distilled triphenylphosphite is dissolved in 10 ml methanol and is added to the green solution taken in a glass stoppered flask and is shaken vigorously. Immediate bright green precipitation started and after 2 hrs., the precipitate is filtered under suction, washed several times with methanol, conc. HCl, water, acetone and ether respectively and dried in vacuum over fused CaCl_2 . The yield is approximately 3 gm. A further crop of compound is isolated from the mother liquor by keeping it overnight (0.5 g.).

Bright green bis-triphenyl phosphite tetrachlorouranium (IV) is insoluble in most common solvents. It is stable in air, water or even in dilute mineral acids. A typical analysis of this compound corresponds to the formula $\text{UCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$. Calcd.: U, 23.75; Cl, 14.17; P, 6.18. Found: U, 23.56; Cl, 14.23; P, 6.32%. The compound on heating gradually changes its colour to give brown uranium dioxide. In conc. HNO_3 it slowly dissolves to give a green solution and on warming quickly oxidises to yellow colour. It readily reduces Ag^+ in AgNO_3 solution to metallic Ag and ammoniacal Cu^{2+} to Cu^+ . The compound rapidly hydrolyses in presence of alkalis and slowly in ammonium hydroxide to give brown $\text{U}(\text{OH})_4$. When fused with excess of α, α' dipyridyl at 200° , it gives a brown product. This brown mass dissolves in HCl to give a green solution from which a deep-green compound slowly precipitated out. Both the derivatives have not yet been well characterised and studies to characterise them are in progress. A very interesting transformation of the original compound takes place when it is boiled in excess of phenol. Phenol, *o*- and *m*-cresol and resorcinol have been tried and in all these cases the green colour of the compound changes to pinkish-white and when well washed repeatedly with methanol and acetone and dried in vacuo gives the composition identical to that of the green compound.

* Partly supported by a UGC grant.

Found : U, 23.60; Cl, 14.41; P, 6.02%. However, this pinkish-white form is not very stable and changes to original green form slowly even when treated with water. These green and pinkish-white compounds may be cis-trans isomers. Insolubility of these compounds in common solvents have prevented their molecular weight measurements and two polymeric forms cannot be excluded at this time.

For the preparation of these compounds, all reagents used are either A.R. or G.R. variety except triphenyl phosphite. The C.P. grade of triphenyl phosphite is redistilled at reduced pressure (20 mm) before use. Analyses of the constituents are done by adopting standard procedures⁴ (chloride and phosphorus gravimetrically and uranium volumetrically) after decomposing these compounds by alkali peroxide fusion.

Studies on the corresponding other halo compounds and their magnetic and spectral properties are in progress.

I am indebted to Principal H. N. Singh, of this College for giving me constant encouragement and providing necessary laboratory facilities.

REFERENCES

1. W. D. Horrocks, Jr. and R. C. Taylor, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 723.
2. G. Booth, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1964, **6**, 1.
3. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry*, Wiley Eastern Reprint, 1969, p. 1027.
4. I. A. Vogel, *A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, Longmans, Green, 1961, 3rd Ed.